

Mixed-Signal Design and Implementation of CMOS Image Sensor

A Project Report

Submitted in partial fulfilment of the
requirements for the Degree of
MASTER OF TECHNOLOGY
in
Microelectronics and VLSI Design

Submitted by:

Rahul Sharma

SR No: 04-02-01-37-51-21-1-20333

under the guidance of

Dr. Chetan Singh Thakur

Department of Electronic Systems Engineering (DESE)

Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore

Bangalore- 560012 (India)

Aug 2021 - Jun 2023

Acknowledgments

I would like to acknowledge my indebtedness and render my warmest thanks to my supervisor, Dr. Chetan Singh Thakur, for his valuable guidance and precious time in making this work possible. I am thankful to him for motivating the ideas and providing support in making them possible.

I would also like to thank Dr.Kapil Jainwal from IIT Bhilai for his expert advice and insightful discussions as and when required. It would have been all more challenging without his support and consistent feedback.

I acknowledge the contribution of Dr. Niranjan Raj, a post-doctoral researcher in the NeuRonICS lab, Mr. Pratik Kumar, and Ms. Madhuvanti Srivatsav R, who are Research students in the Department of Electronic Systems Engineering. The design tapeout could not have been made possible without their timely support.

I thank all my colleagues at NeuRonICS Lab for maintaining an excellent research environment in the workplace and providing hardware and software help whenever required.

I would also like to express my gratitude to my parent organization Indian Space Research Organisation, for sponsoring me to pursue M.Tech at the Indian Institute of Science.

I also extend warm gratitude to my family and friends, who have supported me in all my endeavors. Lastly, I thank Lord Almighty for all the opportunities and courage to pursue the challenges.

Contents

Acknowledgments	i
List of Figures	v
List of Tables	vii
Acronyms	viii
Abstract	1
1 Introduction	2
1.1 Motivation	2
1.2 Scope of the Project	2
1.3 Contributions	3
2 An overview of CMOS Image Sensors	4
2.1 Factors constituting an Image	4
2.2 Image Information Compression: Optical Image to Digital Image	5
2.3 Light Intensity Measurement	6
2.3.1 p-n junction Photodiode	7
2.3.1.1 Charge Collection Loss	8
2.3.1.2 Internal Quantum Efficiency	10
2.3.1.3 Accumulation Mode	11
2.3.2 Pinned Photodiode	14
2.4 Overview of the Noise Sources in the CIS	15
2.4.1 Photon Shot Noise	16

2.4.2	Dark Current and Dark Current Shot Noise	16
2.4.3	Electronic Noise	18
2.4.4	Spatial Noise	20
2.4.5	Overall SNR	21
2.5	An Overview of CMOS-based Pixel Sensor Architectures	23
2.5.1	Source Follower Based APS	24
2.5.2	Common Source Based APS	25
3	Design and Implementation	27
3.1	CIS Architecture and Electronic Rolling Shutter Timings	27
3.2	Design and Layout of 3T-Active Pixel Sensor	29
3.2.1	Photodiode Layout	29
3.2.2	Pixel Sensor	31
3.2.3	Pixel Active Load	33
3.3	Double Sampling Circuit and Layout	34
3.4	Column-Parallel Analog to Digital Converter	37
3.4.1	Preamplifier	39
3.4.2	Positive Feedback Decision Circuit	43
3.4.3	Comparator Characterisation	44
3.5	Ramp Generator	45
3.5.1	Switched-Capacitor Network for Integrator	47
3.5.2	Specifications for OTA used in Ramp Generator	48
3.6	Digital Double Sampling	52
3.6.1	Timing and operation	52
3.6.2	Design	54
3.7	Sign-off Physical Design Considerations	55
4	Results and Conclusion	57
4.1	Results	57
4.1.1	Analog Block Results	57
4.1.2	Digital Block Results	58
4.1.3	Mixed-Signal Results	59

4.2 Conclusion	61
4.3 Future Work	61
A 4T-Active pixel sensor	63
References	65

List of Figures

2.1	Optical Image information	5
2.2	Basic configuration of Image Sensor	5
2.3	Bayer Color Filter Array	6
2.4	Reverse-biased p-n Junction Photodiode	9
2.5	Photodiode Band diagram under reverse-bias stimulus	11
2.6	p-n junction is formed at a position x_j from the surface ($x = 0$). The depletion width $W = x_p - x_n$	12
2.7	Layer structure in Pinned Photodiode (a), Spatial potential profile (b)	14
2.8	Trap-assisted carrier generation	17
2.9	Magnitude of signal and different noise sources	22
2.10	SNR as a function of read noise ($\sigma_{drk} = 0.1 e_{rms}^- \sigma_{Gcg}$ of 1%)	23
2.11	Circuit topology of Source Follower based APS (a), DC transfer characteristics (b).	24
2.12	Circuit topology of Common Source based APS (a), DC transfer characteristics (b).	25
3.1	Architecture of the proposed High-Speed Column-parallel CMOS Image Sensor	28
3.2	Electronic rolling shutter timing of column-parallel CIS	29
3.3	N-Well PSUB diode in standard TSMC 65 nm (a), which is Customised to be used for 3T-APS (b).	30
3.4	Schematic of 3T Active Pixel Sensor (APS) (a), and its layout (b).	31
3.5	Simulated Layout results for 3T-APS, Pixel output voltage as a function of photocurrent and exposure time.	32
3.6	Schematic of Cascode Current Mirror load for 3T-APS.	34
3.7	Schematic of double sampling (a), its layout (b).	35
3.8	Simulated timing results for double sampling circuit	36

3.9	Architecture of Single Slope ADC (SS-ADC).	38
3.10	High-BW Preamplifier for regenerative Comparator: schematic (a), and its layout (b).	40
3.11	Simulated frequency response (load = 200fF) of Preamplifier over the process variations; gain plots (a), and phase plots (b).	41
3.12	Simulated transient response of Preamplifier loaded with 200fF. The sub-window highlights the response delay.	42
3.13	Positive feedback decision circuit for regenerative Comparator: schematic (a), and layout (b) (x-dimension is enlarged for better visualization).	43
3.14	Simulated delay for the decision circuit as a function of input signal swing.	44
3.15	ICMR characterization of Comparator	45
3.16	Transient response of regenerative comparator; subplot highlights the propagation delay.	46
3.17	Switched-Capacitor Integrator based Ramp Generator.	47
3.18	Indirect-feedback based telescopic OTA used in Switched-Capacitor Integrator	49
3.19	Simulated Frequency Response of Indirect-feedback based telescopic OTA.	51
3.20	Transient response of 2-stage telescopic OTA.	51
3.21	Transient response of Switched-Capacitor Ramp Generator.	52
3.22	Concept of light intensity analog signal conversion into digital word using digital double sampling.	53
3.23	Digital double sampling timing.	54
3.24	BIAS register configuration.	54
3.25	Design of digital double sampling with CO glitch detection and synchronizer.	55
4.1	Layout simulation results Over all the Process Corners for the column SS-ADC, which is derived by the 3T-APS and Switched Capacitor Ramp generator	58
4.2	Simulation Results for the SS-ADC used in Column-parallel CIS.	60
4.3	Snapshot of the CIS design integrated with Padframe.	61
1	4T-Active pixel sensor.	64
2	4T-Active pixel sensor timing.	64

List of Tables

3.1	Signal Loss Improvement using Discharge Switch	36
4.1	Physical verification results	59
4.2	Power, performance, and Area results.	59
4.3	Chip Characteristics.	60

Acronyms

CCD	Charge-Coupled Device
CG	Conversion Gain
CIS	CMOS Image Sensor
DNW	Deep N Well
DR	Dynamic Range
EHPs	Electron-hole pairs
FF	Fill Factor
FSI	Front-side-illumination
FWC	Full Well capacity
NW	N Well
PSUB	P substrate
PW	P Well
QE	Quantum Efficiency
R	Responsivity
SOC	System on chip
SS-ADC	Single Slope ADC
TSMC	Taiwan Semiconductor Manufacturing Company

Abstract

This work presents the mixed-signal design and implementation of a CMOS Image Sensor (CIS) chip using a standard CMOS 65-nm 1P9M process from Taiwan Semiconductor Manufacturing Company (TSMC). The chip integrates an optimized photodiode-based 64X64 pixel array, a column-parallel readout circuitry using Single Slope ADC (SS-ADC), parallel-in serial-out register to store and transfer image data for the Image sensor processor (ISP), and access and control circuitry, etc. To mitigate the spatial noise due to the pixel circuit nonuniformities, it utilized digital double sampling. The chip can acquire the images at a high rate of 1000 frames per second (fps) running at 100 MHz clock and 10-bit resolution. By capitalizing on the benefits of TSMC's 65 nm technology, the chip offers significant improvements in performance, power efficiency, and miniaturization.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

In today's era, the use of electronic imaging goes beyond conventional photography. It includes Artificial Intelligence (AI) vision, autonomous driving, scientific, space and medical imaging, as well as photon counting for scientific instrumentation. The development of modern solid-state imaging started with the invention of the Charge-Coupled Device (CCD) device in 1969. CCD-based imaging reached its peak in the early 2000s with high-end digicams and scientific imaging devices. Contemporary to this, there happened the invention of the CMOS transistor in 1963. With continual improvement in terms of the efficient manufacturing process, miniaturization, on-chip integration, power consumption, and noise performance, the CIS begin to surpass CCD imagers specifically in terms of performance and power efficiency in the late 2000s.

This plethora of imaging applications equipped with the matured CMOS technology opens new horizons and verticals of exploration.

1.2 Scope of the Project

Since there is a ubiquitous demand for the CIS, researchers all around the world are working to improve its performance across power consumption, noise performance, and miniaturization

metrics.

This work attempts to design, implement, and characterize a mixed-signal System on chip (SOC) for the CIS. The SOC has been fabricated in the CMOS 65-nm 1P9M technology from TSMC.

1.3 Contributions

For the realization of the SOC, the following are my major contribution:

- A mixed-signal Analog-On-Top (AOT) design flow has been established for the 65-nm technology in the Cadence design environment. It utilizes the standard cell library for digital logic along with the baseband library for the analog circuit design.
- A comprehensive study and understanding of the CIS design and its implementation, including the various aspects of SOC design, specifically the physical design and verification of the custom analog blocks, complete ASIC flow from RTL to gds file generation for digital blocks, sign-off Analog Mixed Signal (AMS) verification for chip etc.
- Physical design and verification of all the building blocks for CIS, i.e., Pixel sensor, read-out circuitry, Pixel-array accessing and controlling circuits, data storage, and biasing circuits, etc.
- Top-level physical design, integration, and verification of analog and digital blocks.
- Preparing the complete database, including LVS, PEX, DRC, ERC, Antenna DRC, and signoff verification data for chip tape out.
- Preparation for the testing and characterization activities, i.e., vendor finalization for transparent packaging, design inputs for the daughter board to house the chip, and test cases generation.

Chapter 2

An overview of CMOS Image Sensors

This chapter gives an overview account of the imaging essentials, performance matrices of photoconversion, different sources of noise in CIS, and pixel sensor architectures.

2.1 Factors constituting an Image

A still image is constructed by the spatial distribution of light intensity at different wavelengths. That is, the information of the light intensity (i) of color (λ) at each position in two-dimensional space (r) constitutes a still color picture. For color moving images, the time (t) at which light reaches the image also needs to be included. The visible light spectrum is a continuous quantity, ranging approximately from 400 nm to 700 nm. However, for imaging purposes, discretizing it to wavelengths of red, green, and blue color is sufficient. It is because the appropriate ratio of these three primary colors reproduces a broad array of colors. Thus, color information can be considered three-dimensional. Figure 2.1 shows that the distribution of these four factors (i,r,λ,t) in seven dimensions constitute an optical Image.

Figure 2.1: Optical Image information

2.2 Image Information Compression: Optical Image to Digital Image

This section propounds how the imager compressed this gigantic image information (seven dimensions) to a single dimension, i.e., light intensity measurement. The basic device configuration for imaging is shown in Fig.2.2.

Figure 2.2: Basic configuration of Image Sensor

The optical image is focused on its image area; consequently, its equivalent electrical signal information is read out and processed by the rest of the circuitry. As depicted, the image area is a 2-D array of basic picture elements, abbreviated as pixels. Each pixel has a photo-sensing element, which absorbs incident light to generate an electric charge proportionate to the light

intensity. Thus light intensity information is obtained at each pixel output, i.e., $S(x_i, y_j)$. Since pixel location is fixed, x_i and y_j cannot take arbitrary values. Thus the continuous space coordinate has been discretized. In this way, the three-dimensional information of a monochrome still image is compressed into one dimension.

For color still imaging, the most usual way to gather the color wavelength information is by arranging a color filter array (CFA) onto the sensor. Figure 2.3 shows the Bayer CFA arrangement, which is the most used CFA. In it, a pitch of size 2×2 is formed of primary colors with a double-green color filter. Two green filters per pitch are arranged in a checkboard pattern to match the higher green color sensitivity of the human eye. Because there is a color filter per pixel, color information is also embedded in the built-in pixel coordinates. Thus six-dimensional color still image information is compressed into a single dimension of light intensity.

Figure 2.3: Bayer Color Filter Array

Lastly, for color moving imaging, repetitive still images at a constant time interval, determined by the imaging system, are captured and processed. Thus the continuous time factor (t) has been discretized.

2.3 Light Intensity Measurement

As discussed earlier, image acquisition needs a reliable measurement of the incoming light from the object to be imaged. Major solid state devices used for light detection known as

photodetectors are photodiode, photogates, phototransistors, Avalanche photo diode (APD), and photoconductive detectors. For applications which don't need photon level counting, a pn junction based photodiode is appropriate candidate from a fabrication complexity, cost and area point of view. Since photodetection is the most critical part of an imaging system, it is inevitable to discuss its operation principle, the way it is made use in CIS, and its performance matrices.

2.3.1 p-n junction Photodiode

The conductivity of a semiconductor sample can be modulated by the optical generation of mobile carriers. Thus, the light intensity can be quantified by observing its conductivity change. But including a p-n junction for the photodetection is advantageous for better response time and sensitivity. Photodiode better response time is attributed to its shorter transit time resulting from the large velocity of the photogenerated carriers, imparted by the strong field in the depletion region[1]. In a reverse-biased illuminated p-n junction, there is the drift of minority carriers across the junction. Under illumination, there is an additional optical generation of minority carriers in excess of the thermal generation. The resultant current, I is the algebraic sum of the usual diode current, I_d and optical generation current, I_{op} , expressed as

$$I = I_d - I_{op} = I_{th} \left(\exp(qV/K_B T) - 1 \right) - qA g_{op} (L_p + L_n + W), \quad (2.1a)$$

Where

$$\text{Thermal-generation current, } I_{th} = qA \left(\frac{L_p}{\tau_p} p_n + \frac{L_n}{\tau_n} n_p \right), \quad (2.1b)$$

$$\text{Depletion width, } W = \sqrt{\frac{2\epsilon_{si}}{q} \frac{(N_a + N_d)}{N_a N_d} (V_{bi} - V)}, \quad (2.1c)$$

$$\text{Built-in potential, } V_{bi} = K_B T \ln \left(\frac{N_a N_d}{n_i^2} \right), \quad (2.1d)$$

$$\text{Hole diffusion-length, } L_p = \sqrt{D_p \tau_p}, \text{ and} \quad (2.1e)$$

$$\text{Electron diffusion-length, } L_n = \sqrt{D_n \tau_n} \quad (2.1f)$$

where N_a and N_d are acceptor and donor carrier concentration (cm^{-3}), D_p and D_n are hole and electron diffusion coefficients (cm^2s^{-1}), τ_p and τ_n are hole and electron average lifetime (s), p_n and n_p are equilibrium hole and electron concentrations in n and p regions respectively (cm^{-3}), V is applied bias (V), g_{op} is optical generation rate (EHPs/ $\text{cm}^3\text{-s}$), A is junction cross-section area (cm^2), K_B is Boltzmann constant ($1.381 \times 10^{-23} \text{ m}^2 \text{ Kg s}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$), ϵ_{si} is the dielectric constant of silicon (Fm^{-1}), q is an electric charge ($1.6 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$), and T is the absolute temperature (K).

For reverse-bias ($|qV|/K_B T \geq 4$), current I approximates to

$$I = -I_{th} - I_{op} \quad (2.2)$$

- sign signifies current is directed from n to p region. Since g_{op} is proportionate to light intensity, current I provides a linear measurement of the light intensity.

2.3.1.1 Charge Collection Loss

To understand the charge collection loss, it is essential to know how charge generation takes place. In a photo-detector, photons with energy E higher than band gap energy E_g of material are absorbed and cause the EHPs generation. This happens due to the prominent photoelectric effect, also called the photo effect. These EHPs are mobile in nature and so can contribute to electrical conductivity. The spatial distribution of optically generated EHPs is governed by the absorption coefficient α . The absorption coefficient of a material primarily depends on light wavelength and the material's properties itself, such as its composition, density, and molecular structure. For Silicon, α decreases monotonically over the visible light spectrum [2].

For a semiconductor with absorption coefficient α , the light intensity (photons/ $\text{cm}^2\text{-s}$) at a distance x from its surface is given by

$$I(x) = I_0 \exp(-\alpha x) \quad (2.3)$$

where I_0 is Incident light intensity at the surface ($x = 0$). The photo-generated charge carriers need to be collected and transported to the device terminals to contribute to the photocurrent. However, there is a certain fraction of the charge is always lost. The charge loss mechanisms stem from various factors, such as the non-optimum design of junction depth and depletion width for the given light spectrum, material nonidealities resulting in surface recombination, trapping and other recombination centers, and impinging loss, etc. In the Front-side-illuminated (FSI) imager, there is a vertical stack of dielectric and metal layers in the vicinity of the photodiode. This structure absorbs and reflects a significant portion of illumination and resulting loss stands as impinging loss. Modern imaging systems use Back-side-illuminated (BSI) architecture, in which the photo-sensitive surface is directly under the light and thus there is a tremendous improvement in spectral sensitivity [3].

To appreciate the significance of optimum photodiode design for optimum charge collection, a reverse-biased p-n junction diode under illumination is discussed.

Figure 2.4: Reverse-biased p-n Junction Photodiode

In Fig.2.4, a reverse-biased p-n junction is under illumination by photons of $E > E_g$; thus, EHPs are generated all over the structure. In region r1, i.e., the depletion region, there is a strong electric field. Assuming an abrupt doping profile, the maximum value of the electric field at

the junction is given by

$$|E_0| = \frac{2(V_{bi} + V_r)}{W} \quad (2.4a)$$

$$\text{Built-in potential, } V_{bi} = K_B T \ln \left(\frac{N_a N_d}{n_i^2} \right) \quad (2.4b)$$

$$\text{Depletion width, } W = \sqrt{\frac{2\epsilon_{si} (N_a + N_d)}{q} (V_{bi} + V_r)} \quad (2.4c)$$

where N_a and N_d are acceptor and donor carrier concentration (cm^{-3}), ϵ_{si} is dielectric constant of silicon (Fm^{-1}), q is electric charge (1.6×10^{-19} C), and V_r is applied reverse-bias voltage.

This electric field causes these carriers to sweep away the depletion region. Since holes drift in the direction of the electric field while electrons in the opposite direction, there is a current flow from n to p region. In region r2 i.e., diffusion region, which is in the vicinity of the depletion region, there is no net electric field. However, EHPs generated in this region can randomly diffuse towards the depletion region and thus sweep across the depletion region to contribute in the photocurrent. EHPs in region r3, which is far away from the depletion region and has no net electric field also undergo random motion and annihilate by recombination process, thus no contribution to the photocurrent.

Since the photocurrent is mainly contributed by the EHPs collected in the depletion region, having a wider active or depletion region is desirable. This is why the suitable bias condition for the photodetection is reverse bias. The concerned energy band diagram is shown in the Fig.2.5.

2.3.1.2 Internal Quantum Efficiency

Quantum Efficiency (QE) governs the efficiency of a photon absorption and EHP generation. It is the average number of generated Electron-hole pairs (EHPs) out of an average number of incident photons. Photon generation is a stochastic process modeled by binomial law [4]. Accordingly, the probability of generating k EHPs out of n incident photons is given by

$$p(k, n) = \frac{n!}{k! (n - k)!} QE^k (1 - QE)^{n-k} \quad (2.5)$$

Figure 2.5: Photodiode Band diagram under reverse-bias stimulus

Hence, the probability of generating n electrons out of n photons is QE^n . So $p(n, n)$ will decrease exponentially with n for QE smaller than 1. Thus, QE is a very critical parameter for photodetection sensitivity. Assuming there is negligible EHPs collection from the diffusion region for p-n junction photodiode, then the average number of EHPs generated is equivalent to light absorbed in the depletion region. The QE can be expressed as

$$QE = \frac{\int_{x_p}^{x_n} I_0 \exp(-\alpha x) dx}{\int_{-\infty}^0 I_0 \exp(-\alpha x) dx} = \exp(-\alpha x_n) [1 - \exp(-\alpha W)] \quad (2.6)$$

For given α , QE tends to 1, only if x_n tends to zero and W tends to infinity. Practically W is finite, then junction location, x_j will also affect QE . Since α value is lower for long-wavelength illumination [69 jun ohta], photons penetrate deeper in silicon before they are absorbed. In this case, to optimize QE , a deeper junction is desirable. Although a wider depletion region results in better QE and lower junction capacitance c_j but attributes to a larger transit time. Thus there is a trade-off between QE and speed of response.

2.3.1.3 Accumulation Mode

For a typical-size silicon photodiode, the photocurrent in daylight is in the range of hundreds of fA to tenths of pA [2]. While it is possible to measure such a low photocurrent, it is difficult

Figure 2.6: p-n junction is formed at a position x_j from the surface ($x = 0$). The depletion width $W = x_p - x_n$

to precisely measure photocurrents of the same order from a two-dimensional array for a large number of points at a video rate.

For such a scenario, the better approach is to integrate or accumulate the photo-generated charge in the pre-charged photodiode capacitance. The photodiode is charged to a reverse voltage (less than its breakdown voltage) and then open-circuited (n terminal is floated and p terminal is grounded) while under continuous illumination. The generated charge carriers are swept over the depletion region by the electric field, where the holes sink into the ground through the substrate, and photoelectrons are accumulated in the n region and compensate for the positive space charge. Thus there is a shift from an electrically neutral junction to a net negative charge junction. This space charge removal can be interpreted as the discharge of space charge capacitor by the photocurrent. The rate of space charge removal is linearly proportionate to light intensity.

In Accumulation mode, there is no net current. The sum of the usual diode current and the photocurrent is balanced by the displacement current.

$$I_{th} + I_{op} = -C_{pd}(V(t)) \frac{dV(t)}{dt} \quad (2.7)$$

The space charge capacitance, C_{pd} depends on the doping profile, material property, junction geometry, and potential across PD. It can be approximated as the parallel plate capacitance,

given as

$$C_{pd}(V(t)) = \epsilon_{si} \frac{A}{W} = \epsilon_{si} \frac{A}{K(V + V_{bi})^n} \quad (2.8)$$

where n models the doping profile: $n = 1/2$ for a step junction and $1/3$ for a linear junction, and K is a constant.

Substitution for $C_{pd}(V(t))$ in (2.7) from (2.8) and rearrangement of terms results in a separable variable ODE that is integrated as

$$\int_{V(0)}^{V(t)} (V + V_{bi})^{-n} dv = - \int_0^t \frac{K}{\epsilon_{si}} (I_{th} + I_{op}) dt \quad (2.9)$$

Solving for $v(t)$, yields into expression:

$$V(t) = (V_0 + V_{bi}) \left[1 - \frac{(I_{th} + I_{op})(1-n)}{C_0(V_0 + V_{bi})} t \right]^{\frac{1}{1-n}} - V_{bi} \quad (2.10)$$

Where V_0 and C_0 are the initial values of the voltage and capacitance in PD, respectively. From (2.10) it can be established that PD potential $V(t)$ decreases with time at a rate that depends on both time and the light intensity. Under illumination levels that predominate the dark current, this decay rate is nearly constant with respect to time[2].

Since light intensity level affects the space charge removal rate, so does the voltage drop rate, it can be quantified by the voltage difference at two time instants. one of the time instants is the initial instant at which the diode is reverse biased, and the other is decided based on factors such as light intensity levels, PD responsivity, and frame rate of the imager etc.

$$\Delta V = V_0 - V(t = t_0) = (V_0 + V_{bi}) \left[1 - \left[1 - \frac{(I_{th} + I_{op})(1-n)}{C_0(V_0 + V_{bi})} t_0 \right]^{\frac{1}{1-n}} \right] \quad (2.11)$$

For (2.11), assuming $(1-n)t_0/(C_0(V_0+V_{bi}))$ a constant, $K1$ and carrying out Taylor expansion about $I = (I_{th} + I_{op}) = 0$, results into expression:

$$\Delta V = (V_0 + V_{bi}) \left[\frac{K1}{1-n} I - \frac{nK1^2}{2(1-n)^2} I^2 + \frac{n(2n-1)K1^3}{6(1-n)^3} I^3 - \dots \right] \quad (2.12)$$

As shown in Fig. 2.7 (a), it has effectively two junctions, p^+ -n and n-p. For this p^+ -np structure with its p^+ and p regions at zero potential, under assumptions of depletion approximation and abrupt junction, it can easily conclude that the maximum potential occurs in the n region where electric field becomes zero[5]. This potential is also known as pinned voltage, given by

$$\text{Pinned voltage, } V_{pin} = K_B T \ln \left(\frac{N_a^+ N_d}{n_i^2} \right), \quad (2.14)$$

where N_a^+ and N_d are the impurity carrier concentrations (cm^{-3}) in p^+ and n regions respectively. This expression happens similar to the built-in potential of p^+ -n junction. Since the structure is under equilibrium, the overall built-in potential will be the highest of the individual built-in potentials of these junctions. As per (2.14), the overall V_{bi} will be governed by the p^+ -n junction. Hence the pinned voltage of the p^+ np structure is the built-in potential of the highly doped junction, i.e., p^+ -n.

As discussed for the photodiode, under illumination, the photoelectrons start accumulating at the location of maximum potential i.e., in the n region, and effectively neutralize the positive charge in the n region. As shown in Fig. 2.7(b) this net decrease in charge causes the potential to decrease. The significance of the V_{pin} being in n region is that, under illumination, the charge accumulation happens to be away from the surface, and thus no mobile charge loss by the surface traps. This is why PPD results in higher QE for lower wavelength illumination. The reduction of the surface trap density also results in a lower dark current.

The description of how this structure breaks the trade-off between G_{cg} and FWC and lowers the reset noise will be carried out in the Appendix. A.

2.4 Overview of the Noise Sources in the CIS

In a CIS imaging system, the ubiquitous presence of noise sources in the signal chain, specifically from the photodetection to analog signal readout, distorts the signal.

2.4.1 Photon Shot Noise

The photons incidence, and so EHPs generation in a photo sensing material is a statistical phenomenon. The arrival of each photon is an independent random event occurring with the same probability p . In an interval Δt , if the average number of photons incident on the photo-sensing material is N_{ph} then the probability of exactly n photons arriving in the same time interval is given by the Poisson distribution as:

$$p_n(\Delta t) = \frac{\exp(-N_{ph}) N_{ph}^n}{n!} \quad (2.15)$$

The magnitude of the photon shot noise, expressed as standard deviation, is therefore expressed as:

$$\sigma_{sn} = \sqrt{N_{ph}} \quad (2.16)$$

This square root dependency of photon shot noise deteriorates the slope of the SNR (dB) versus the number of photons plot from 20 dB/dec to 10 dB/dec. Assume a CIS has a conversion gain G_{cg} and N_{ph} photons incidence on it in a Δt time interval, then the variance of the output signal V_o can be expressed as[4]

$$\sigma_{V_o}^2 = G_{cg}E[V_o] + \sigma_{V_{dark}}^2 \quad (2.17)$$

where $\sigma_{V_{dark}}^2$ is output signal variance under no illumination which is the dark noise of the imager. From (2.17), a plot of variance versus average output signal, known as the photon transfer curve (PTC), can be used to measure the conversion gain, which is the slope of PTC in the linear region.

2.4.2 Dark Current and Dark Current Shot Noise

In a semiconductor material, there is always a thermal generation recombination (G-R) of charge carriers even in the absence of light. The different G-R mechanisms in the depletion area give rise to the dark current. since for a given dark current, the larger the integration time

(T_{int}), the higher unintended readout signal change so the maximum (T_{int}) is limited by it. Because it is directly affected by the temperature, only cooling the imager can mitigate its effects. Trapping centers, originating from the impurities and defects at the surface and interfaces between different materials, play a significant role in the dark current generation. These traps act as steps between conduction and valance bands and thus aid in the transitions of carriers as shown in Fig.2.8.

The underlying analytic formulation for the dark current generation is governed by Shockley-

Figure 2.8: Trap-assisted carrier generation

Hall-Read equation [6], according to which the net G-R rate R_{gr} is expressed as:

$$R_{gr} = \frac{A_{csp}A_{csn}V_{th}(pn - n_i^2)N_t}{A_{csn}\left(n + n_i \exp\left(\frac{E_t - E_{fi}}{K_B T}\right)\right) + A_{csp}\left(p + n_i \exp\left(\frac{E_{fi} - E_t}{K_B T}\right)\right)} \quad (2.18)$$

where A_{csp} and A_{csn} are the hole and electron cross-section area (cm^2), V_{th} is the thermal voltage(V), $E_t - E_{fi}$ is an energy gap (eV) between the trap and intrinsic Fermi level. The rest of the parameters have the usual meaning and unit, as outlined earlier. Since at thermal equilibrium $np = n_i^2$, so R_{gr} becomes zero. This signifies there is no dark current generation at thermal equilibrium. But the depletion region in a reverse-biased p-n junction is not in thermal equilibrium and the dark current increases almost linearly with its width [5]. Thus depletion width can not be increased arbitrarily to meet the better QE and Conversion gain specifications.

The noise caused by the dark current is quantified by its associated shot noise. The dark current shot noise variance, observed over integration interval T_{int} is given as:

$$Q_{drk}^2 = I_{drk} T_{int} \quad (2.19)$$

2.4.3 Electronic Noise

Till now the major noise sources related to photodetection have been discussed. As outlined earlier, the accumulated charge associated with the light intensity level is quantified by a voltage drop. This voltage drop is read out by a set of electronic circuits that are designed by using MOS transistors, capacitors, resistors, etc. So it is worth understanding the different noise sources and their modeling in these primitive components.

1. **Resistor Thermal Noise and $K_B T/C$ Noise** In a conducting device operating at positive absolute temperature, the fluctuation of charge carriers velocity due to thermal excitation gives rise to thermal noise. The resulting random fluctuation in the electrical response is modeled by the zero-mean Gaussian distribution. Thus it is quantified by the variance or standard deviation. since its amplitude is highly uncorrelated in time, it has equal power distribution over the whole frequency spectrum, more precisely, up to the THz range at room temperature. This attributes to its constant power spectral density, which is a useful parameter to analyze circuits noise performance in the frequency domain.

The thermal noise in a resistor (R) can be modeled as either a noise voltage source (v_n) in series of noiseless resistor or a noise current source (i_n) parallel to the noiseless resistor, provided that $(v_n) = (i_n)R$, where (v_n) and (i_n) are some statistical matrices for noise voltage and current respectively. The corresponding power spectral densities (PSD) for the noise voltage and current source are expressed as:

$$S_v(f) = 4K_B T R \quad (2.20a)$$

$$S_i(f) = \frac{S_v(f)}{R^2} = \frac{4K_B T}{R} \quad (2.20b)$$

where all the parameters are usual, which have been outlined earlier.

The variance of the noise voltage across a capacitor connected with a resistive element is found to be $K_B T/C$. Observe that it is independent of the resistance value; this is because thermal noise PSD across the capacitor and bandwidth of the RC circuit are inversely

related.

2. **MOS Transistor Thermal and Flicker noise** The thermal noise generation mechanism in MOS is similar to that in a resistive element. Likewise in a resistor, for MOS also, thermal noise can be modeled as either a noise current source ($i_{n,mos}$) from drain to source or noise voltage source ($v_{n,mos}$) in series of gate. The ($i_{n,mos}$) and ($v_{n,mos}$) are related by transconductance, and the corresponding PSDs of voltage and current noise sources are given as[7]:

$$S_i(f) = \mu 4K_B T \frac{|Q_I|}{L^2}, \quad (2.21a)$$

where Q_I is the channel inversion charge

$$Q_I = \begin{cases} \mu C_{ox} \frac{W}{L} (V_{GS} - V_T) & \text{triode region} \\ \frac{2}{3} \mu C_{ox} \frac{W}{L} (V_{GS} - V_T) & \text{saturation region} \end{cases} \quad (2.21b)$$

$$S_v(f) = \frac{S_i(f)}{g_m^2} \quad (2.21c)$$

where V_T is the MOS threshold voltage (V), W and L are the channel width (m) and length (m), C_{ox} is per unit area gate capacitance (F/m²), and g_m is MOS transconductance(A/V). In a CIS imager, the capacitance of either the photo-sensing area or the charge detection node is reset to a predefined value before the charge integration takes place. It is executed by a MOS switch in series with this capacitor. Since the thermal noise generation in MOS is similar to register, it can be shown that thermal noise PSD across this capacitor is of the form $K_B T/C$.

In addition to thermal and quantum noise (shot noise) in electronic devices, there is also the prevalence of noise with its PSD obeying inverse frequency relation. This low-frequency noise is denoted by $1/f$ noise or flicker noise. The random trap and release of some of the moving charge carriers at si-sio₂ interface introduce the flicker noise [19,20 from ultra-low noise]. Although this noise has been well-characterized experimentally, no exact mechanism underlying its origin has been identified. One of the commonly used

methods model it as a voltage source in series of gate, and in the saturation region, its PSD is given as

$$S_{v,flk} = \frac{K}{C_{ox}WL} \frac{1}{f} \quad (2.22)$$

where K is a process-dependent parameter (V^2F), and f is the frequency (Hz). For nanometer (nm) CMOS technology, the actual $1/f$ noise power is much more complex and depends on more design factors.

2.4.4 Spatial Noise

The spatial variation in output responses of the identical pixels and readout circuits under uniform illumination is termed spatial noise. Since for a given CIS imager, the spatial noise pattern is fixed, it is also typified by Fixed Pattern Noise (FPN). Although the actual expression for the output voltage for a given intensity level depends on the architecture of the pixel and readout chain, majorly it depends on photo-sensing device spectral response, its dark current generation, V_{th} and β of MOS transistor, and capacitance, etc. All these parameters depend on the process parameters; thus after fabrication even two identical designed circuits are not identical. This is the root cause of the FPN.

For sake of convenience, FPN can be addressed as a linear combination of Pixel FPN and Column FPN under two meaningful conditions, i.e., under dark and with illumination.

In the dark, the pixel FPN is caused by the pixel-to-pixel dark current non-uniformity and MOS transistor mismatches. The FPN arising due to transistor mismatches is mitigated by using the double sampling algorithm, in which the difference between two sample levels, corresponding to the pixel reset state and post-exposure state, is taken.

Under illumination, the pixel-to-pixel response non-uniformity (PRNU) along with the above mismatches give rise to Pixel FPN. PRNU is a collective measure for the non-uniformities in photon collection, photon-to-charge conversion, and charge-to-voltage conversion processes.

The Column FPN in an image manifests as vertical stripes and is easily noticeable. This constraints stringent specification on column FPN, typically better than 0.1 %, while the acceptable

Pixel FPN is relatively relaxed, i.e., 0.5 % [8].

The FPN characterization in CIS can be done by spatial variance over the pixels array of the temporal average of the signal and is expressed as [4]:

$$\sigma_s^2[E_t[V_o]] = \frac{\sigma_s^2[G_{cg}]}{G_{cg}^2} E_{st}[V_o]^2 + \sigma_{V_{off}}^2, \quad (2.23)$$

where $E_t[V_o]$ is temporal average of pixel output, E_{st} is average over both space and time, σ_s^2 is spatial variance, G_{cg} is the conversion gain, and V_{off} is the residual offset voltage.

2.4.5 Overall SNR

SNR is one of the critical performance parameters that infer the image quality. The major discussed noise sources affect the SNR differently based on the illumination level. A simplified expression for CIS imager is

$$SNR = 10 \log \left[\frac{N^2}{\sigma_{sn}^2 + \sigma_{drk}^2 + \sigma_{fpm}^2 + \sigma_{rd}^2} \right] \quad (2.24)$$

where $N = QE_t N_{ph}$ is the average number of photoelectrons collected in the active region. QE_t is the overall quantum efficiency including optics efficiency and PD internal QE. In the denominator, noise sources are quantified by their input-referred standard deviations, expressed in e_{rms}^- . σ_{sn} is expressed in (2.16). σ_{drk} denotes dark current shot noise

$$\sigma_{drk}^2 = N_{drk}^2 \quad (2.25)$$

where N_{drk} is the average number of electrons generated by the dark current in integration time (T_{int}).

σ_{fpm} is magnitude of the input-referred FPN. Assuming negligible FPN in the dark, then

$$\sigma_{FPN}^2 = \sigma_{G_{cg}}^2 N^2 \quad (2.26)$$

σ_{rd} is the accumulative input referred read noise, consisting of thermal, 1/f, and shot noise.

Figure 2.9: Magnitude of signal and different noise sources

Figure 2.9 plots the magnitude of these noises as a function of input photoelectrons (accumulated over typical T_{int} of μs order) for typical values of $\sigma_{drk} = 0.1 e_{rms}^-$, σ_{Gcg} of 1%, and $\sigma_{rd} = 1 e_{rms}^-$. It is evident that photon shot noise dominates in the mid-signal range, FPN noise in the higher signal levels provided the imager has not been saturated, while for lower illumination levels, read noise is of importance. Figure 2.10 compares noise magnitude with respect to signal level by plotting SNR and highlights the requirement of lower read noise for lower illumination levels.

Figure 2.10: SNR as a function of read noise ($\sigma_{drk} = 0.1 e_{rms}^- \sigma_{Gcg}$ of 1%)

2.5 An Overview of CMOS-based Pixel Sensor Architectures

In the imaging system, the pixel is the front-end building block responsible for photo-sensing, charge-to-voltage conversion, and facilitating its access in the pixel array. The potential drop corresponding to the illumination level is readout and digitized using ADC for post-image processing in the digital domain. In this readout chain, the low noise amplification must be at the earliest stage to achieve better SNR. It is accomplished by pixel-level amplification, and the corresponding architecture is attributed as an Active pixel sensor (APS). The main advantage of the APS is the isolation provided between the pixel sense node and column parasitic capacitance else, the parallel combination of both results in large capacitance of the order pF (typically)[9]. This corresponds to 160 nV signal swing for unit charge integrated in PD or PPD which is too weak to measure even at room temperature. The other spin-off advantages of this

isolation are higher sensitivity and better noise performance but the cost of higher FPN and the lesser ratio of photosensitive area to pixel area, i.e., fill factor. However, both shortcomings are not problematic, as the former is dealt with by double sampling and later by using smaller node technology and microlens on top of the photo-sensitive areas[10].

A single MOS transistor can be configured as a small signal voltage amplifier in three topologies while in saturation region [sedra]. In common gate configuration, input sees the low impedance, which will not let PD or PPD accumulate the charge during exposure. Hence source follower (SF) and common source topologies are most commonly used in CMOS APS.

2.5.1 Source Follower Based APS

Figure 2.11: Circuit topology of Source Follower based APS (a), DC transfer characteristics (b).

In this configuration, the amplifying element, i.e., the MOS transistor is used in the common drain topology, in which the input signal is applied to its gate terminal, and the response is taken from the source terminal. The sensing node, which is either PD or FD or PPD is connected to the gate terminal. The use of active load, realized using NMOS, maximizes the output signal swing [sedra]; also it provides current biasing, which is robust against V_T and process

parameter (K) variations.

In Fig 2.11 the DC transfer plot is shown, from this it is clear that the input signal can have a wide swing, which is required for high dynamic range (HDR) applications. This also facilitates an easy reset in the sense that the reset value need not be exact but can be a range. Thus this readout scheme provides immunity against reset switch non-idealities.

2.5.2 Common Source Based APS

Figure 2.12: Circuit topology of Common Source based APS (a), DC transfer characteristics (b).

In Fig. 2.12 (a) the sense node is connected to the gate terminal while output is taken from the drain terminal across the PMOS based active load. This load also biases the common source amplifier. The DC transfer plot shown in Fig. 2.12 (b) infers (1) with respect to the source follower topology, the input signal swing has been reduced by its gain factor. (2) the requirement of a precise feedback reset value. On exercising the reset, V_{out} is determined by the convergent solution of current across diode-connected MOS (Common source transistor after feedback reset) and overdrive voltage requirement of the PMOS load for the given V_{bias} . Consequent to the

reset removal, for faithful signal amplification, this V_{out} value must lie in the linear region of the transfer curve of Fig. 2.12 (b), say the quiescent point Q2. If the quiescent point happens in the saturation part, say Q1, then there will be no signal amplification. This highlights the criticality of precise reset value. Even the charge injection of the reset switch can push the quiescent point out of the linear region. Owing to all these constraints, We will confine to SF-based APS topologies.

Chapter 3

Design and Implementation

This chapter discusses the various design aspects of the major building blocks used in this work. The major design blocks for the CIS Imager include 1. Pixel array 2. Signal readout chain 3. Data storage 4. Pixel array accessing and controlling circuitry, and 5. Biasing and clock unit. These functional blocks include both analog and digital blocks, thus, a mixed signal design flow is utilized. The column circuitry consists of the SS-ADC and the storage element, i.e., parallel-in serial-out register (PISO). The SS-ADC has a sampling unit followed by the comparator and counter. Another input to the SS-ADC is the ramp signal, which is generated by the Switched-capacitor based Ramp generator. The accessing and controlling units for the pixel array includes the Row decoder and Reset decoder, respectively.

3.1 CIS Architecture and Electronic Rolling Shutter Timings

Figure 3.1 shows the overall block diagram of a high-speed column-parallel CIS. The pixels array is at the center of the imager. It occupies most of the chip's silicon area. Each pixel comprises a photodiode with at least one amplifying transistor and two MOS switches for reset and row selection. In order to achieve high frame rates, a column parallel readout scheme is generally performed. The pixels array is read line by line, and all the pixels of the same line are read in parallel. Hence, RST and RS decoders are implemented to reset the pixel elements and

to make a row selection.

Figure 3.1: Architecture of the proposed High-Speed Column-parallel CMOS Image Sensor

As discussed in the previous chapter, a difference between the reset level and sensor signal level gives a measure of the light signal. So, a double sampling block is used to store both samples.

Figure 3.2 shows the timing diagram of the proposed CIS readout chain. Since the pixel structure is the 3T-Active Pixel sensor, so readout can be done in the rolling shutter mode only. In

Figure 3.2: Electronic rolling shutter timing of column-parallel CIS

this scheme, the image data is read out on line by line. At the end of the integration time, the sensor signal level is sampled by the Sig_samp switch, followed by the immediate sampling of the reset signal level. So RS switch is made high to read these two samples successively. Observe each row is reset two times, this is because the first reset is not readout. Reading the reset sample and then waiting for the sensor signal for the entire integration time will result in an extremely low-speed system. Also, it will make the CIS speed depend on the integration time, which practically is not feasible. However, the samples corresponding to the sensor signal and second reset are not correlated; thus in this architecture, reset noise cancellation is not achieved.

3.2 Design and Layout of 3T-Active Pixel Sensor

3.2.1 Photodiode Layout

The available diodes in the standard submicron TSMC 65 nm technology are N^+/P Well (PW), P^+/N Well (NW), PW/Deep N Well (DNW), DNW/P substrate (PSUB), and NW/PSUB. The critical performance parameters to make use of a photodiode in solid-state imaging are its

photo-sensitivity (quantified by QE and Responsivity (R)), Conversion Gain (CG), Full Well capacity (FWC), and dark current. As discussed in the previous chapter, all these parameters depend on the physical properties (doping concentration, effective dielectric, implantation dose and energy, etc.) and bias conditions. Qualitatively, a wide depletion width (W) results in low junction capacitance, and so high CG, high QE and so high R, but lower speed and large dark current. Since out of the available standard diodes, both N^+ / PW , P^+ / NW will have comparatively narrower W , so they are not considered.

Figure 3.3: N-Well PSUB diode in standard TSMC 65 nm (a), which is Customised to be used for 3T-APS (b).

Figure 3.3(a) shows the standard NW/PSUB diode, in which PSUB and N-Well constitute the p and n regions, respectively. The N^+ and P^+ impurities are implanted in these regions onto which ohmic contacts are accessed through tungsten vias to the metal layer (M1). Since this is a standard process in which only Front-side-illumination (FSI) is feasible, light impinges on the N-Well. To make N-Well transparent for illumination, N^+ , M1, and vias are removed, and only single contact from the N-Well is provided 3.3(b). In APS (3.4), the positive terminal of the diode is grounded, which is the default case for PSUB, so P^+ , M1, and vias are also removed 3.3(b).

3.2.2 Pixel Sensor

Figure 3.4 (a) shows the schematic of the active pixel sensor, it has one MOS transistor for Reset, one for Row access (in 2D pixel array), and one as SF amplifier making it a 3T-active pixel sensor (3T-APS). The PD is reverse-biased or reset to a value of $AV_{DD} - V_{th}$, if the RST signal 'ON' level is AV_{DD} and V_{th} is the threshold voltage of reset MOS transistor. To maximize the FWC and so the upper limit of Dynamic Range (DR), the reset signal level must have the maximum possible magnitude for the given process (this level must be below the breakdown voltage of the diode). In TSMC 65 nm process, the maximum drive level is $3.3V \pm 10\%$, and so is the chosen value of AV_{DD} . The compatible transistor to this level is the I/O transistor having thick gate oxide.

Figure 3.4: Schematic of 3T Active Pixel Sensor (APS) (a), and its layout (b).

As shown in Fig.3.5, consequent to the RST release, pixel voltage decreases monotonically at a slope depending on the light intensity level. In the enlarged part in Fig.3.5, there is a dip of approx. 40 mV in pixel output level due to the RST switch non-idealities, in particular, due to charge injection during MOS switching from 'ON' to 'OFF' state. To minimize charge injection, channel charge must be reduced [11], which for a given overdrive ($V_{gs} - V_{th}$), is achieved by

choosing a minimum dimensions ($W/L = 500\text{nm}/500\text{nm}$) MOS (Although it slows the reset operation, but that is not critical).

Figure 3.5: Simulated Layout results for 3T-APS, Pixel output voltage as a function of photocurrent and exposure time.

The DC gain for SF amplifier is given by

$$G = \frac{g_m R_L}{1 + (g_m + g_{mb}) R_L} \quad (3.1)$$

where g_m and g_{mb} are the transconductance (S) and body transconductance (S) respectively, R_L is effective load, a parallel combination of load and output conductance (g_{ds}). For a given DC current (I_{bias}) in the saturation region, g_m is given by

$$g_m = \sqrt{(2I_{bias} \beta_n)} \quad (3.2)$$

where, β_n is product of process parameter ($\mu_n C_{ox}$) and ratio W/L .

In SF the output follows input by an offset of V_{gs} , which for constant current bias (I_{bias}) in the saturation region, given by

$$V_{gs} = V_{th} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{2I_{bias}}{\beta_n}\right)} \quad (3.3)$$

The input referred thermal noise PSD for SF with active load (NMOS) is given by

$$\bar{V}_n^2 = \frac{8K_B T \mu_n}{L^2} \left(\frac{1}{gm1} + \frac{gm2}{gm1^2} \right) \quad (3.4)$$

From (3.1) and (3.4), for high gain and better noise performance, g_m must be high, which requires the high value of I_{bias} and W/L ratio, but these high values will trade-off the output signal swing (3.3). Also, a large W/L ratio reduces the Fill Factor (FF). Thus the values of design parameters I_{bias} and W/L are selected for optimum FF, signal swing, and noise performance.

From (2.13), and Fig. 3.5, the PD capacitance is approx. 25 fF. It gives CG of $6.4 \mu\text{V}/e^-$ and FWC of $39,000 e^-$. The layout is optimized to have a FF of approx. 50%.

3.2.3 Pixel Active Load

To maximize the SF small signal gain, ideally, R_L must be infinite (3.1). A reasonable load of 1 Mohm value realized either as OD, poly, or NW resistor in TSMC 65 nm process requires a minimum area of $1652 \mu\text{m}^2$, which is a huge area overhead. Also, IR loss in passive load kills signal swing and generates thermal noise, so an active load is used. This active load also biases the SF.

Figure 3.6: Schematic of Cascode Current Mirror load for 3T-APS.

As shown in Fig. 3.6, to reduce the current variation due to pixel output voltage variation (drain voltage of M_{C1}) a cascode topology is used[11]. We have used native transistors for cascode devices, which have almost zero threshold voltage [12], and this results in a lower compliance voltage for the external reference current source (I_{ref}). Although this topology is not a high-swing configuration, the lower value of the bias current ($0.5 \mu A$) and negligible V_{th} of M_{C1} (approx 20 mV) results in almost constant bias current for the pixel output voltage upto 200 mV. (a negligible current drop of 10% at a pixel output voltage of 200 mV).

3.3 Double Sampling Circuit and Layout

As outlined in Chapter 2, double sampling (DS) reduces the pixel APS FPN due to transistor mismatches. As shown in Fig.3.7, it uses two capacitors, one each for signal and reset path. Although it is possible to implement DS using a single cap, it slows down the CIS overall speed. This is because the reset operation for successive rows can be done only when the previous row reset and signal level are converted by the column ADC. Since the pixel output traverse from approx 1.6V to 0V (although below V_{th} level, due to subthreshold operation, its slope decreases substantially), so NMOS-based switches are used.

After the integration, first, the integrated signal value is sampled on C_{sig} capacitor by making

Figure 3.7: Schematic of double sampling (a), its layout (b).

RS 'ON' followed by sig_samp switch to 'ON' state. Consequent to C_{sig} capacitor charged to a steady value, the sig_samp is switched 'OFF'. It is then followed by the reset signal sampling on C_{rst} capacitor by switching RST_samp switch to the 'ON' state. Then hold switches (RST_hold and Sig_hold) pass the sampled values in succession (first reset signal) to the column ADC to achieve digital double-sampling (Fig. 3.8).

Since the sampling capacitors are not alike to ideal voltage source, the residual charge at the parasitic capacitor at 'vs' node (C_{vs}) affects the charge transfer between these nodes. The resultant signal loss ratio can be avoided if the ratio C_{rst}/C_{vs} can make infinitely large, which is not feasible. The other approach to mitigate this signal loss to a great extent is to reset C_{vs} to zero potential before either of the signals, stored on the C_{sig} and C_{rst} capacitors, is passed to it.

Figure 3.8: Simulated timing results for double sampling circuit

Table 3.1 illustrates the effectiveness of the inclusion of the Discharge switch.

Table 3.1: Signal Loss Improvement using Discharge Switch

Test Case	Voltage at 'vs' node WITH- OUT Discharge Switch	Voltage at 'vs' node WITH Discharge Switch
$V_R = 1.6\text{V}, V_{sig} = 0.2\text{V}$ ($\Delta = 1.4\text{V}$)	1.4V and 0.4V ($\Delta = 1\text{V}$)	1.4V and 0.2V ($\Delta = 1.2\text{V}$)
$V_R = 1.6\text{V}, V_{sig} = 1.4\text{V}$ ($\Delta = 0.2\text{V}$)	1.4V and 1.4V ($\Delta = 0\text{V}$)	1.4V and 1.2V ($\Delta = 0.2\text{V}$)

To reduce the switch non-idealities effect (clock feedthrough and charge injection), the switches are sized to the minimum dimensions ($W/L = 0.5\mu/0.5\mu$). TSMC 65 nm standard process has both Metal-Insulator-Metal (MIM) and Metal-Oxide-Metal capacitors, out of these, the former provides better capacitance density and lower parasitics. The available MIM capacitor is implemented as a parallel plate capacitor between Metal Layer 7 (M7) and Metal Layer 8 (M8), having a density of $2\text{fF}/\mu\text{m}^2$. The availability of MIM in the top layers leverages the bottom metal layers for interconnections.

3.4 Column-Parallel Analog to Digital Converter

Since digital signal processing has better noise immunity, it is better to digitize the analog signal at the earliest possible stage in any electronic system. In the case of CIS, the only analog signal, i.e., light intensity, can be digitized at three stages, namely at the chip level, at each column level, or at each pixel level. For the given resolution and speed, the bandwidth requirement increases from pixel-level to chip-level digital conversion. Larger the bandwidth of a system, the higher the integrated noise in it. It makes pixel-level digital conversion the best choice. However, column-level digital conversion is the most practically used method because, to date, it is the most viable configuration to achieve both resolution and speed. In this CIS architecture, there is an ADC for each column, so it is typified as Column-Parallel ADC.

Out of the most commonly used column-parallel ADCs, namely Single Slope, Successive Approximation, Cyclic, and $\Delta\Sigma$ -type[13], the SS-ADC is a small size and simple architecture, useful for low to medium speed and resolution ranges. In this work, a SS-ADC is adopted with a 10-bit resolution running at a clock rate of 100 MHz.

In the SS-ADC architecture (Fig.3.9), the sampled analog value is given to the comparator, which compares it with a Ramp signal. Wherever there is agreement between these two values, a decision is taken by the comparator, either high or low. Thus comparator is a mixed signal block, which takes analog inputs and outputs digital signal. The major specifications required for the comparator block are as follows:

Figure 3.9: Architecture of SS-ADC.

1. **Gain** The gain of the comparator is an important parameter, which dictates its resolution. The resolution of the comparator is the minimum input change required to make a decision. For a ramp signal ranging from 2.2V to 0.2V, in duration which accommodates the swing of a 10-bit counter running at 100 MHz, the step size:

$$\Delta V = \frac{(2.2 - 0.2)}{2^{10} - 1} = 1.955 \text{ mV} \quad (3.5)$$

The comparator must respond within ΔV change in its differential input. For this resolution, the required minimum open loop gain:

$$G_{oc} = \frac{V_{OH} - V_{OL}}{\Delta V} = \frac{3.3 - 0}{1.955 \times 10^{-3}} \approx 1688 \frac{V}{V} \approx 64.55 \text{ dB} \quad (3.6)$$

Assume the margin, to accommodate temperature and process variation effect on the gain, is 6dB, then the required gain will be 70.55 dB.

The comparator is operating with only a positive supply, so the lower limit is set to zero. Also, the upper limit at 3.3V is set to accommodate the reset level from the sensor.

2. **3-dB Bandwidth** The comparator must settle down within one clock period, once a decision is made. This ensures the quantization error is within one step size. By dominant

pole approximation, the comparator can be treated as a single-pole system, then required 3-dB bandwidth

$$BW \geq \frac{4}{t_{ss}} \geq \frac{4}{T_c} \geq \frac{4}{10 \times 10^{-9}} \geq 400 \text{ MHz} \quad (3.7)$$

where t_{ss} and T_c are the settling time (s) and clock period (s), respectively. A margin factor of four shall be sufficient to accommodate process and temperature variation then the minimum required 3-dB bandwidth is 1.6 GHz.

The resultant GBW product is too high to realize with conventional topology, so a high-speed comparator topology is chosen, which utilizes the positive feedback to reduce its settling time.

This high-speed topology makes use of both negative and positive feedback mechanisms in such a way that the overall response time is lower than that of the individual stages[14]. In this method, a preamplifier is used to build up the input change to a sufficiently large value and then apply it to the latch. The preamplifier must have high bandwidth to reduce the delay, this is because, at this stage, signal magnitude is small, and so speed is solely determined by the bandwidth.

3.4.1 Preamplifier

In Fig.3.10, to realize the high bandwidth, the dominant poles at the Po1 and Po2 nodes are pushed to a higher value by reducing resistive impedances seen at these nodes. The diode-connected MOS works as a two-terminal device with the equivalent ohmic impedance of $1/g_m$, which is much lower than the $1/g_{ds}$ (In the case of TSMC 65 nm for W/L ratio of (1um/1um), g_m ranges from 6K ohm to 13K ohm while $1/g_{ds}$ ranges from 273 Kohm to 6.9 Mohm).Assuming MOS transistors $M1 \equiv M2$, $M3 \equiv M4$, and $M5 \equiv M6$, then the dominant poles are located at:

$$P = -\frac{g_{m1}}{C} = -\frac{g_{m2}}{C} \quad (3.8)$$

Where C is net capacitance (F) at any either Po1 or Po2 node due to parasitic and the successive

stage load. In the absence of M5 and M6, The open loop small-signal gain is:

$$G_{op} = -\frac{g_{m1}}{g_{m3}} = -\frac{g_{m2}}{g_{m4}} \quad (3.9)$$

Figure 3.10: High-BW Preamplifier for regenerative Comparator: schematic (a), and its layout (b).

This gain is very small, even for the large differences in W/L values. The inclusion of M5 and M6 increases the current across the M1 and M2 and thus increases their g_m values. The resultant increased gain is expressed as:

$$G'_{op} = -\frac{g_{m1}}{g_{m3}} = -\sqrt{\frac{K_p(W_1/L_1)I_1}{K_n(W_3/L_3)I_3}} = -\sqrt{\frac{K_p(W_1/L_1)}{K_n(W_3/L_3)}} \sqrt{1 + \frac{I_5}{I_3}} \quad (3.10)$$

Thus the gain has been enhanced by the factor of $\sqrt{1 + \frac{I_5}{I_3}}$.

Figure 3.11: Simulated frequency response (load = 200fF) of Preamplifier over the process variations; gain plots (a), and phase plots (b).

For a conservative load of 200 fF, the 3-dB bandwidth over the process corners (even corners typical-typical (TT), slow-slow (SS), fast-fast (FF), and odd corners slow-fast (SF) and fast-slow (FS)) is ≈ 36 MHz (Fig. 3.11 (a)). There is a good phase margin of ≈ 124 deg (Fig. 3.11 (b)), which can also be corroborated from the clean transient response without shots on the edges (Fig. 3.12).

Figure 3.12: Simulated transient response of Preamplifier loaded with 200fF. The sub-window highlights the response delay.

In Fig. 3.12 the output is saturated at either ≈ 0 V or 1.4 V levels. For the given bias current, this output swing is constrained by the diode-connected transistors M5 or M6. Since this output level is sufficient to drive the latch properly, to be discussed in the following section, the preamplifier is biased at a low bias current value of $40 \mu\text{A}$. The propagation delay for this load, as highlighted in the subplot (Fig. 3.12), is ≈ 8 ns. It is improved to 2 ns for the actual load (from the following decision circuit load) of ≈ 50 fF.

Since the CIS architecture is a parallel column, the pitch circuitry must match that of the pixel array column. Fig. 3.10 (b), the width or pitch is only $6.4 \mu\text{m}$.

3.4.2 Positive Feedback Decision Circuit

A back-to-back connection of two inverters constitutes a latch and so positive feedback. In Fig.3.13, the positive feedback of M1 and M2 speeds up the speed of the decision. The propagation delay of the latch depends on its time constant, the magnitude of the initial voltage difference at the nodes Co1 and Co2, and the output swing. For a symmetrical latch, the propagation delay is expressed as[14]:

Figure 3.13: Positive feedback decision circuit for regenerative Comparator: schematic (a), and layout (b) (x-dimension is enlarged for better visualization).

$$t_p = \tau_l \ln \left(\frac{V_{OH} - V_{OL}}{2 \Delta V_{in}} \right) \quad (3.11)$$

where ΔV_{in} is initial voltage difference given by

$$\Delta V_{in} = V_2(t = 0) - V_1(t = 0) \quad (3.12)$$

and τ_l is time-constant of latch, given as:

$$\tau_l \approx \frac{C}{g_m} = 0.67 C_{ox} \sqrt{\frac{WL^3}{2K} I} \quad (3.13)$$

Thus for given current I , τ_l is reduced with minimum size transistors, and so both M1 and M2 are sized at $0.5\mu\text{m}/0.5\mu\text{m}$. M3 and M4 work as current sources, controlled by the amplified signal by the preamplifier.

The propagation delay, as a function of the input signal swing (v_i), is plotted in Fig. 3.14.

Figure 3.14: Simulated delay for the decision circuit as a function of input signal swing.

In this plot, the propagation delay (t_p) is the difference between the time instant at which normalized output swing approaches zero and the initial time (9 ns). For instance the t_p for $v_i = 1.5\text{V}$ is $\approx 5\text{ ns}$. As discussed earlier, t_p is decreasing monotonically with increasing v_i . The 5 ns delay for $v_i = 1.5\text{V}$, along with the 2 ns delay for the preamplifier block, results in a delay of $\approx 7\text{ ns}$, which is smaller than one clock period (10 ns).

3.4.3 Comparator Characterisation

1. **Input Common Mode Range** The sensor signal ranges from 0 V to $\approx 1.6\text{ V}$, which can be further increased by using SF with native MOS to $\approx 2.1\text{ V}$.

Figure 3.15: ICMR characterization of Comparator .

In Fig. 3.15, one of the inputs is swept from 0.2 V to 2.2 V for each step of another input, which is 500 mV. For every step, the output is changing swiftly with equal gain (slop of this the curves).

2. **Transient Response** Transient characterization is of importance since it gives the dynamics while inputs are varying, which is the practical case. In Fig. 3.16, at one of the inputs, a rectangular periodic signal of 0 to 2.2 V is applied, while the other is constant. This test vector causes one side of the diff-pair to switch from cut-off to saturation, and thus it is a conservative measure of propagation delay. An enlarged portion of this plot in the sub-window highlights the (t_p), which is ≈ 7 ns.

3.5 Ramp Generator

The ramp generator in the ADCs is a critical building block since the performance of the ADCs depends a lot on the accuracy of the ramp signal. Sensor noise, FPN, linearity, and yield characteristics depend greatly on the ramp generator design and specifications. First of all, because the ramp signal drives an ADC in every column, it needs to be immune to kickback noise from

Figure 3.16: Transient response of regenerative comparator; subplot highlights the propagation delay.

the ADC array. Second, because of the global distributed nature of the ramp signal, it can be a major source of supply noise induced row-wise noise. Third, any nonlinearity in the ramp is translated into the DNL and INL error of each ADC directly. The ramp generator must therefore have good driving capability, fast settling, good supply rejection, and excellent linearity. In principle, different design approaches generate the ramp signal increasing or decreasing a signal in voltage, current, or charge mode. This is implemented by using voltage DAC, current DAC, and capacitive DAC or with an integrator in continuous or discrete time response.

Figure 3.17 shows a Switched-capacitor based Integrator Ramp Generator topology in which charge is transferred between capacitors C_s and C_f periodically with the help of an Operational transconductance amplifier (OTA), and thus output node potential is changed at a constant rate. The main advantage of this method is its simplicity and low area and power requirement. The major functional blocks in this topology are 1. Switch Capacitor Network (SCN). 2. OTA 3.

Figure 3.17: Switched-Capacitor Integrator based Ramp Generator.

Clock division unit, and 4. Biasing generation unit. The Ramp Enable (RE) switch in the feedback path of the integrator control the start of the conversion timing of the counter. For a 10-bit SS-ADC running at a 100 MHz clock rate, the ramp signal needs to traverse the dynamic range (0-2.0 V) in a time duration of $2^{10}T_{clk}$, i.e., $10.24 \mu s$. This dictates its minimum slope. However, as seen in the following subsection, this slope is highly dependent on the clock stability and process variations, so a higher slope of $\approx 0.23 V/\mu s$ is taken against the required slope of $0.195 V/\mu s$.

3.5.1 Switched-Capacitor Network for Integrator

For the required slope of the ramp signal, with a typical on-chip capacitor of the order of a few hundred fF, the required current is of order 10^{-8} amps. This needs a resistance of the order of hundreds of Mohm, which is not feasible from an area and the process variation point of view. One of the methods to realize such a large value resistance is by using the switch-capacitor circuit, in which charge is transferred at a constant rate between two terminals held at the fixed potentials. The equivalent resistance is expressed as:

$$R_{SC} = \frac{1}{C f_{clk}} \quad (3.14)$$

where C and f_{clk} are the capacitance (F) and the clock frequency (Hz), respectively.

In Fig.3.17 V_p is greater than V_{mns} , and the ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are the compliment phase of a non-overlapping clock. During the ϕ_1 phase, the capacitor is charged to $C_s(V_p - V_{mns})$, while in the ϕ_2 phase, both nodes of the capacitor are at the same potential, i.e., V_p (assuming there is perfect virtual short in the OTA, so that $V_m = V_p$), and capacitor C_s is now connected to the rest of circuit. Thus there is a gain of charge on the left plate of C_s , and so a current flows into the C_f , causing $V_{rp}(t)$ to decrease. The rate of decrease can be given as:

$$\frac{dV_{rp}(t)}{dt} = -\frac{C_s}{C_f} \Delta V_i f_{clk} \quad (3.15)$$

where $\Delta V_i = V_p - V_{mns}$.

In 3.15, the capacitors are in ratio, which in an IC fabrication is almost independent of the process and temperature variations. This is the main advantage of using a Switched-capacitor circuit in the integrator design.

To achieve the negative slope of $0.23 \text{ V}/\mu\text{s}$, the values of $C_s/C_f = 150 \text{ fF}/400\text{fF}$ and $\Delta V_i = 2-1.9 = 100 \text{ mV}$ is taken.

3.5.2 Specifications for OTA used in Ramp Generator

The major OTA specifications required for the current CIS Imager are derived as follows:

1. **Gain** The finite open loop gain in an Op-amp violates the virtual short condition [11].

This makes V_m to be different from the V_p , and thus ΔV_i is changed. From (3.15), it will change the slope of the ramp signal. The slope sensitivity with respect to the change in ΔV can be expressed as:

$$\Delta V = \Delta V_i - V_d \quad (3.16a)$$

$$\text{Sensitivity } S = \frac{\partial S/S}{\partial V_d/V_d} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{\Delta V_i}{V_d}} \quad (3.16b)$$

Figure 3.18: Indirect-feedback based telescopic OTA used in Switched-Capacitor Integrator

where V_d is the voltage difference between V_m and V_p , and thus change the ΔV_i to ΔV . From (3.16b), V_d of 1 mV gives rise to 1 % change in S . since open loop gain is related to V_d by :

$$V_o = A_{ol} V_d \quad (3.17)$$

so for output level at 2V, the minimum A_{ol} for V_d of 1 mV comes out 66 dB.

2. **Bandwidth** Since the input signal V_{mns} and V_p are constant signals, so ideally there is no BW requirement for the OTA. However, the integration is not continuous but discrete in time. Here at every 100 ns, there is a step change in a charge equivalent to ≈ 2 mV. Such a small magnitude is amplified linearly (for the gain ≥ 60 dB and rail voltage of 3.3 V), so for a faster response, a large BW is desirable. A 20 MHz BW shall be sufficient.
3. **Input Common Mode Range and Output Common Mode Range** Since OTA is working in negative feedback and V_p is held constant at 2.2 V, so ideally, OTA needs to work at this common mode voltage, this is why the NMOS-based diff-pair has been chosen (Fig. 3.18). The OTA shall be able to have an output swing from 0-2.2 V. In Fig. 3.18, the lower

limit of the output swing is close to zero (≈ 125 mV).

4. **Slew Rate** As outlined earlier, OTA is working in the linear region for the required slope. However, SR can be calculated on the basis of the fact that the output must be able to follow the input step of 2 mV in a minimum of 50 ns, which gives an $SR \geq 40$ mV/ μ s.

To achieve these specifications, a telescopic two-stage topology is selected. In which the active load for the diff-pair is the cascode-based current mirror, consisting of M3, M4, M7, and M8. Accordingly, the diff-pair has been cascaded by the current buffers consisting of M5 and M6. The second stage is a simple common source amplifier. The compensating capacitor C_c is not directly connected between the output node and diff-pair output node; rather, the current through it is feedback indirectly through the M6. This provides an LHP zero at:

$$Z = -\frac{gm_6}{C_c} \quad (3.18)$$

This is in contrast to the conventional 5-transistor OTA in which the direct feedback compensation gives rise to the RHP zero, which degrades the stability. The dominant pole is given approximately at:

$$P1 = -\frac{G_1}{C_1 + \left(\frac{G_1}{G_2}\right)C_2 + \frac{gm_{II}}{G_2}C_c} \quad (3.19)$$

where G_1 , G_2 are the net output conductances (s) seen at the first and second stages, respectively. Similarly, C_1 and C_2 are the net capacitances (F) at the first and second stages.

Since the Ramp Generator needs to drive the 64-column simultaneously, a large load of ≈ 3.2 pF is offered by the column array. From the DC simulation, the P1 comes out at ≈ 9.6 KHz, which is close to the simulated value of ≈ 7 KHz. The UGF for this OTA can be expressed as:

$$f_{ugf} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{gm_I}{C_c} \quad (3.20)$$

where gm_I is the transconductance (s) of the first stage diff-pair. The calculated and simulated values of the f_{ugf} at 28 MHz and 27.6 MHz are closely matched (Fig. 3.19).

Figure 3.19: Simulated Frequency Response of Indirect-feedback based telescopic OTA.

Figure 3.20: Transient response of 2-stage telescopic OTA.

The transient response shown in Fig. 3.20 ensures that the output is able to follow the input

signal step of 10 mV in a maximum time of 25 ns over all the corners, resulting in an $SR \geq 400$ mV/ μ s, which is much better than the specification.

In Fig.3.21 ramp signal is reset to its top limit by setting the RE signal to high, and it starts to roll down once RE is released. The slope precision over the process corners depends on how precise the ΔV generation and clock unit are. To have precise ΔV generation, a resistor divider network is used, which provides process variation of better than 1% in the TSMC 65 nm process using the poly resistors.

Figure 3.21: Transient response of Switched-Capacitor Ramp Generator.

3.6 Digital Double Sampling

3.6.1 Timing and operation

From Fig. 3.22, it is inferred that the digital word equivalent of the light intensity signal is proportionate to the difference between two count numbers. The slope of the ramp signal (S) is selected such that the maximum count value corresponds to the upper limit of the dynamic range.

$$V = S\Delta T = SNT_{\text{clk}}$$

$$\text{LightIntensity} \propto (V_2 - V_1)$$

$$= S(N_u - N_d)T_{\text{clk}}$$

Figure 3.22: Concept of light intensity analog signal conversion into digital word using digital double sampling.

To realize the count difference, as shown in Fig. 3.23, a preloaded counter is first made to down count for the reset signal followed by the up count for the sensor signal. The counter operation is controlled by two control signals, namely RE (ramp enable), which is external to the chip, and second is CO (comparator output). It starts the counting in syn with the ramp generator signal, controlled by RE, and freezes on the low to high transition of CO. Thus, after these two counting operations, the counter reaches the value:

$$CNT = BIAS + [N_u - N_d] \quad (3.21)$$

where BIAS is a 10-bit digital word that preloads the counter. The counter is preloaded before the conversion of each row. It is programmable over binary equivalent values of 400 to 912 using bits b9, b8, b7, and b4. The bits b4, b7, and b8 are made short and programmed using a single control line, data478 (Fig. 3.24). The programmable range is chosen for the reset signal variations over process corners. It ensures that over the process, voltage, and temperature (PVT) variations, the counter shall not undergo underflow during reset signal underflow.

Figure 3.23: Digital double sampling timing.

Figure 3.24: BIAS register configuration.

3.6.2 Design

Figure 3.25 shows the state diagram to realize the digital double sampling. In addition to the above discussion in the previous subsection, there is a provision to detect the glitches in the CO. The states S2 and S6 check the integrity of the CO signal for a duration of the four counts cycles; if in this duration, there is a change in the CO signal, the controller goes back to the previous counting operation (S1 and S5, respectively).

Since BIAS digital word is programmable over a wide range, the counter shall not undergo underflow or overflow. Still, for reliable operation, there is an additional provision for the counter's lower and upper bounds check.

Since CO is an asynchronous signal, a two-flip flop synchronizer is used to avoid metastability.

Figure 3.25: Design of digital double sampling with CO glitch detection and synchronizer.

3.7 Sign-off Physical Design Considerations

To realize an optimum and integral physical design, the following considerations have been taken during the physical design:

1. The sensitive circuits are enclosed by the appropriate potential guard rings. This is important because, in column-parallel architecture, the abrupt switching in one column disturbs the operation of the adjacent columns. Additionally, it prevents the latch-up phenomenon in circuits consisting of both NMOS and PMOS transistors.
2. To prevent the ground bounce and voltage droop due to the inadvertent switching on the supply lines, the bypass capacitor, realized as MOSCAP is placed nearest to the supply line. The leakage power consumption of these MOSCAPs is negligible because they are operating at the IO supply levels, i.e., 3.3 V.

3. To minimize the FPN due to performance mismatches among pixels and columns, apart from the process variations, these must be uniform supply distribution. In a SOC, supply is provided from one of the die edges and is supposed to have uniform spatial distribution over the whole chip area. This is ensured by using the power rings and stripes, having minimal IR drop and the least parasitic loading to adjacent signal lines.
4. The electrical performance matching of the two components depends on their orientation and environment in the die. To minimize the mismatch effects, good layout practices are adopted, i.e., dummy device placement and common-centroid, etc.
5. In a mixed-signal SOC, the noisy digital ground must be isolated from the rather sensitive analog blocks at the silicon level itself. In our work, it is implemented by using the DNW around the digital blocks.
6. For reliable Chemical Mechanical Processing, the design must fill minimum density requirements, so dummy base and metal fill are carried out at the sign-off stage. But it must not be done on the top of the pixel array area so that there is no obstruction for the incoming light.

The chip has one serial data output (SO) and one transfer pulse (TPS). Each pad has High voltage diodes, which are back-to-back connected to safeguard the design from ESD. Around the die, there is a sealing, which is not part of the actual design but is required to provide any protection against any inadvertent ESD phenomenon during the fabrication cycle.

Chapter 4

Results and Conclusion

This chapter discusses the top-level physical and functional validation results. The signoff physical and functional verifications for both analog and digital blocks are carried out by the industry standard physical tools. On successful completion of exhaustive verification checks specific to the fabrication process, the graphic data system (gds) file is generated for tape out.

4.1 Results

4.1.1 Analog Block Results

In Fig. 4.1, the comparator output is switching from low to high whenever the ramp signal is approaching either of the sample values. The resultant variation in the magnitude of the sample value and ramp signal slope is reflected by the instances at which the comparator is switching. The off duration, between the instances at which the ramp signal starts downwards and the instant at which the comparator is switching from low to high, is the measure of the sample value.

Figure 4.1: Layout simulation results Over all the Process Corners for the column SS-ADC, which is derived by the 3T-APS and Switched Capacitor Ramp generator

4.1.2 Digital Block Results

Apart from the external control inputs(Clk, POR, data478, data9, RE), the comparator output (CO) also controls the digital logic functionality, and since It is asynchronous in nature, a 2-flop synchronizer is used.

The netlist generation and physical implementation for the digital blocks are done in the cadence tool, while the physical verification is done using Calibre, a physical verification tool. The sign-off timing closure is checked by Tempus, a tool from cadence, while the power, IR, and EM verifications are carried out by the Voltus. The physical verifications carried out include Design Rule Checks (DRC), Electrical Rule Checks (ERC), and Antenna DRC.

Table 4.1 list the physical verification results.

Physical Verification	Status	Remark
DRC Check	density violations	closed by base and metal fill
ERC Check	NIL	
Antenna DRC Check	NIL	

Table 4.1: Physical verification results

The performance verification results for the digital logic are summarized in table 4.2

Parameter	Value
Clock period	10 ns
Setup slack	2.732 ns
Hold slack	0.185 ns
Area	0.070125 μm^2
Total Power Consumption	3.155 mW

Table 4.2: Power, performance, and Area results.

In the table 4.2, since there is a good amount of the $\approx 26\%$ setup slack, we have optimized the original design power consumption using the HVT library cells.

4.1.3 Mixed-Signal Results

Figure 4.2 shows the mixed-signal simulation result for the SS-ADC. As soon as the Power on reset (POR) is released (not shown in the results), the bias register is loaded with a 10-bit value. The counter starts the conversion in sync with the Ramp signal, controlled by the RE, and stops

conversion on the low-to-high transition of the CO signal. In the first phase, the counter has undergone a down count from 400 to 187, while in other, it up counts to 506. This is a complete readout of one row. This digital double-sampling word is serially pumped out of the chip at the clock rate in sync with the TPS_out pulse. Observe counter has been loaded to bias value before the next row conversion .

Figure 4.2: Simulation Results for the SS-ADC used in Column-parallel CIS.

Table 4.3 summarizes the chip characteristics.

Parameter	Value
Process	65 nm 1P9M
Supply Voltage	3.3V/1V
Pixel Array Size	64X64
Maximum Frame rate	1000 fps
Total Power Consumption	48 mW at 1000 fps
Die Area	0.26 mm ²
Conversion Gain	4.6 μ V/e ⁻

Table 4.3: Chip Characteristics.

4.2 Conclusion

In this work, we have successfully designed and implemented a high-speed column parallel-based CMOS Image sensor in the standard 65-nm 1P9M process. Figure 4.3 shows a snapshot of the undertaken design integrated with the pad frame.

Figure 4.3: Snapshot of the CIS design integrated with Padframe.

Out of the various applications, this work in submicron CMOS technology will be specifically useful for AI-based image processing hardware realization, which prefers the submicron process technology.

4.3 Future Work

To test and characterize the fabricated design, the following activities are under progress.

1. **Transparent-Lid Packaging**

A special QFN package with a glass lid is planned for the packaging.

2. **Daughter Card PCB Design**

To test the chip, a no of external control signals (To control the integration time, slope, conversion time, and digital bias, etc.) and biasing references are required. For the same, a design is in progress.

3. Frame Analyzer

To analyze the image captured, a sophisticated frame grabber from the Matrox-Radiat is acquired. A study is underway to understand its interface with the chip.

Appendix A

4T-Active pixel sensor

The 4T-APS topology is similar to 3T-APS except for the inclusion of the Pinned PD and transfer gate (TG). In Fig 1, the PPD and floating diffusion (FD) makes the photosensitive part. Since the PPD is not externally reverse-biased to create the active region for the collection of photo-generated charge, the potential profile of the PPD must ensure the complete depletion of the entire n region.

Assuming the PPD is fully depleted, then the EHPs generation takes place under illumination. Since the p^+ and PSUB are at zero potential, only the positive charge in the active n region is compensated, which can also be interpreted as photoelectrons accumulation. To transfer this accumulated charge in the PPD to the FD, 1. the potential barriers of the junctions n/PSUB and n^+ /PSUB must bring down, and 2. the potential of the n^+ shall be higher than the pinned voltage of the PPD. The TG, like in a MOS, achieves the former, and the latter is achieved by resetting FD at potential $A_{VDD} - V_{th}$.

Figure 1: 4T-Active pixel sensor.

In Fig. 2, first FD is reset by RST and sampled by the Reset_samp immediately followed by the transfer of the accumulated charge from PPD to FD by TG and sampled by Sig_samp. Since both the samples belong to the same RST pulse, they are correlated and thus enable the correlated double sampling (CDS).

Figure 2: 4T-Active pixel sensor timing.

Since the photodetection and photo-sensing nodes are separate nodes, thus there is no tradeoff between the FWC and CG.

The dark current reduction, and high QE, specifically for lower wavelengths along with the CDS, make this APS an industry standard for electronic imaging with read noise at least comparable to CCD [4].

For ultra-fast imaging, the 4T-APS can be made to use in global shutter mode. In global shutter mode, there is simultaneous integration timing. The integration starts at the same instant by the coincidental TG timing. The global shutter operation control sequence is 1. first reset pulse (RST1) to enable the charge transfer 2. TG to transfer the charge 3. Immediate second reset pulse for double sampling. Since there is an integration time difference between the RST1 and TG, so RST1 is not sampled. Thus reset noise for both samples belong to the different reset pulses, thus non-correlated sampling. Therefore both global shutter and CDS operation are not possible simultaneously.

References

- [1] B.E.A. Saleh and M.C. Teich. *Fundamentals of Photonics, 2 Volume Set*. Wiley Series in Pure and Applied Optics. Wiley, 2019.
- [2] J. Ohta. *Smart CMOS Image Sensors and Applications*. Optical Science and Engineering. CRC Press, 2020.
- [3] Sony's latest image sensors and the technologies that lies behind them. <https://www.sony.com/en/SonyInfo/technology/stories/imagesensor7tech/>. Accessed: 2023-02-25.
- [4] A. Boukhayma. *Ultra Low Noise CMOS Image Sensors*. Springer Theses. Springer International Publishing, 2018.
- [5] B.G. Streetman and S. Banerjee. *Solid State Electronic Devices*. Prentice-Hall series in solid state physical electronics. Pearson/Prentice Hall, 2006.
- [6] W. Shockley, R.N. Hall, and W.T. Read Jr. Statistics of the recombinations of holes and electrons. *Physical Review*, 87(5):835, 1952.
- [7] Noise in mos transistors; input and output referred noise,lec-25. <https://nptel.ac.in/courses/117106030/>. Accessed: 2022-09-25.
- [8] Low-noise cmos image sensors for radio-molecular imaging. <http://resolver.tudelft.nl/uuid:38d9e021-b5ec-48f8-8aea-93a4393a0478/>. Accessed: 2023-07-01.

- [9] Cmos image sensors,lec-4. <http://isl.stanford.edu/~abbas/ee392b/lect04.pdf/>. Accessed: 2023-05-20.
- [10] Edward A. Watson, Donald T. Miller, and Kenneth J. Barnard. Fill factor improvement using microlens arrays. In M. Edward Motamedi and Rolf Goering, editors, *Miniaturized Systems with Micro-Optics and Micromechanics III*, volume 3276, pages 123 – 134. International Society for Optics and Photonics, SPIE, 1998.
- [11] R.J. Baker. *CMOS: Circuit Design, Layout, and Simulation*. IEEE Press Series on Microelectronic Systems. Wiley, 2011.
- [12] Native transistor. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Native_transistor/. Accessed: 2023-05-20.
- [13] T. Kuroda. *Essential Principles of Image Sensors*. CRC Press, 2017.
- [14] P.E. Allen, B. Dobkin, R. Dobkin, D.R. Holberg, J. Williams, and Elsevier Science & Technology (Firm). *CMOS Analog Circuit Design*. Analog Circuit Design: A Tutorial Guide to Applications and Solutions. Oxford University Press, USA, 2011.